

Excipients for mRNA Delivery

About Us

The active ingredients of mRNA vaccines are usually encapsulated in lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) to protect mRNA from degradation and efficiently complete the intracellular delivery of mRNA. Lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) have emerged across the pharmaceutical industry as promising vehicles to deliver a variety of therapeutics.

CD Bioparticles is a leading supplier of LNP delivery materials, providing customers with various high-quality lipid excipients (mRNA delivery system excipients). Our facility is ISO9001 and ISO13485 certified and manufactures products at scale for global customers according to ICH Q7A guidelines. At present, we have a variety of nucleic acid delivery excipients with independent intellectual property rights, and can customize the production according to customer requirements. Many of our products (including customized structures) have been verified by many mRNA vaccine manufacturers and widely recognized by our customers.

Today we offer you:

Right excipient and lipids, which are essential for successful encapsulation.

- Manufacturing of pharmaceutical excipients
- Cationic lipids encapsulating negatively charged mRNA
- PEGylated lipids contribute to the formation of a protective hydrophilic layer, thereby sterically stabilizing LNP
- Custom and portfolio lipids options for the different types of lipids you need to create stable LNPs and protect the mRNA

Product Name	CAS No.	Structural Formula
mPEG2000-OH	9004-74-4	$\text{CH}_3\text{O}-(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_n\text{H}$
mPEG2000-CM	16024-60-5	$\text{CH}_3\text{O}-(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_n\text{CH}_2-\text{COOH}$
mPEG-DPPE	205494-72-0	
mPEG-DSPE	147867-65-0	
mPEG-DMG	160743-62-4	
ALC-0159 mPEG-DTA	1849616-42-7	
ALC-0315 DHA	2036272-55-4	
SM-102 HUO	2089251-47-6	
D-Lin-MC3-DMA	1224606-06-7	
DSPC	816-94-4	
DOTMA	104872-42-6	

Product Name	CAS No.	Structural Formula
DOSPA	168479-03-6	
DOTAP	132172-61-3	
ePC	1246304-44-8	
DLin-MC3-DMA	1224606-06-7	
C12-200	1220890-25-4	
ALC-0315	2036272-55-4	
cKK-E12	1432494-65-9	
306O ₁₁₀	2322290-93-5	
BAME-O16B	2490668-30-7	
TT3	1821214-50-9	
9A1P9	2760467-57-8	

Product Name	CAS No.	Structural Formula
FTT5	2328129-27-5	
DOPE	4004-05-1	
Cholesterol	57-88-5	
DC-Cholesterol	137056-72-5	
β -sitosterol	5779-62-4	
BHEM-Cholesterol	624742-83-2	
DDAB	3700-67-2	

Contact Us

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